
Issues and Challenges of the Weekly Market in Maharashtra: A Special Reference to Karad taluka of Satara District

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Abstract:

Weekly market is not only place for available goods to the villagers but also providing sell opportunity for local produce and minor forest product in rural area. People who live in rural area not possible to go to town or city for shopping for basic requirement likes-daily needs etc. In Study area, Major portion of the population depends on agriculture and milk products. Nearest surrounding all villagers visit to the weekly market to purchase. They sell those surplus produce in near weekly market. Weekly markets play important role in rural areas providing employment and income generation process. But it is observed that rural weekly markets in Karad taluka have been facing many issues and challenges due to the number of factors that affect the smooth transactions in the market and its growth. The purpose of this paper to identify some of the issues in the weekly market that seller and buyers are facing through the personal visit and interviews with the sellers and buyers, it was found that the weekly markets in many places lack even basic facilities to run the market. e.g., compound wall, market shed, toilet, hospital, dustbins, security control system etc. During the interview it was found that the local authority of the markets needs to develop the basic facilities of the market for smooth transactions and growth of village economy. In this paper has focused on infrastructure of the weekly market places.

Keywords: Weekly Markets, Village Economy, Rural Area

Introduction:

About 70% of India's peoples live in rural areas. Almost one third of the national income created from rural India. Rural markets are an important part of the total market of India. In rural area permanent market facilities is not available so weekly markets play importance role for available basic needs there. It gives various opportunities, whether for marketing durables, garments, daily used goods or financial services. The rural marketer is faced with an entirely different set of conditions and problems when marketing in rural areas as compared to urban areas. For the successful way of rural markets, a basic requirement is infrastructure. The lack of such infrastructure is aggravating the distribution challenges in rural India.

Weekly market is very historic concept of trade and commerce, in ancient time also concept of weekly market was there and people used to buy and sell and exchange. Weekly market is also called 'Haat', Bazar. They continue to play a vital role in the rural economy these markets provide people an opportunity not only to purchase consumer goods, but also to sell surplus agricultural and allied products.

Each weekly market caters to the need of a minimum of 10 to a maximum of 50 villages, drawing around 4000 persons who come to buy and sell a range of daily needs. Market is held on weekly bases. Sellers sell in one weekly markets on one day and move to another on the next day. It is a place to sell and buy various types of goods for example vegetables, fruits and

pulses. Weekly market is trading place of local small traders on specific day of every week to sell their goods.

Two types of sellers were sold his goods under this market they are as permanent seller and temporary seller. Permanent seller had permanent shops for trading of goods with permanent sheds other than temporary sellers because they are selling his goods at temporary place. They are not regular so they set up a shop for the day and close them on the day of evening.

Review of Literature:

- 1 Saxena, H. M. (1988)¹ has explained in his book “Rural Markets and Development” about the weekly market that, the development of fairs(mela) and weekly markets (haat, bazaar) were landmark in the field of rural marketing, both these rural trading institutions, wherever developed are still continue to serve the needs of rural people.
- 2 Aggarwal, P. K. (2007)² Point out in his book “Tribal development planning in India” tribal’s, exploited by government agencies and contractors in marketing of non-timber forest product.
- 3 Hasnain, N. (2007)³ his book “Tribal India” Mention that Tribals area regular market are still a rarity among them. In most of the cases people assemble in an assigned place and on an appointed time and exchange their commodities wish each other. The market held in tribal regions usually trade in commodities of local use like vegetables, cereals, meat, spices, salt, utensils, agricultural tools and implements clothing, cosmetics etc.

Objectives of Studies:

- 1 To study the profile of weekly market in Satara district.

- 2 To examine the issues and challenges of weekly market in Karad taluka of Satara district.

Methodology:

The study is analytical in nature and confined only to Karad taluka in Satara district where the numbers of weekly markets are more. This study is based on both primary and secondary data. For collection of primary data, 10 rural weekly markets from Karad taluka are selected. Further from each market 10 sellers and 10 buyers are selected randomly for the purpose of the study altogether 50 buyers and 50 sellers are interviewed using a questionnaire. The secondary data are collected from various books and published articles from journals and local government offices.

Selection of Study Area and Sample:

Present study is based on Satara district of Maharashtra state. Satara district is included total 11 tehsils the purpose of present study, we have selected only the Karad taluka of satara district. In the karad taluka have 217 villages under the 204 Grampanchayats. There are 19 rural weekly market in study area. We have to selected 10 weekly market (Rural area) places. We have visited to the sampled weekly market on the market day and interviewed the sellers and buyers with the help of questionnaires and collected important information from the marketing point of view.

Weekly markets:

70 % population living in rural areas. Only 30% population lives in urban area. Urban area people fulfil all basic requirement by big market like- Big shops, Shopping malls, Big Bazaar and Super markets etc, but rural population not able to purchases the commodity from urban market, mean while they are also want to purchases the all commodity of urban shop. In Maharashtra these types of problem solve by weekly markets, mainly in rural area

stabilized a market in a week in the village. Nearest surrounding all villagers visit to the weekly market purchase to all type daily

needs as like- vegetables, fruits, cloths and foods etc. below the table show weekly markets status of Satara district.

Table -1: Taluka wise weekly markets in Satara district

Weekly Markets		
Taluka	No of village	No of weekly market
Khandala	65	06
Phaltan	125	12
Wai	126	05
Mahabaleshwar	110	01
Javali	153	07
Koregaon	138	11
Khatav	139	21
Man	104	16
Satara	205	12
Patan	338	15
Karad	216	19
Total	1719	125

Source: <http://www.satara.gov.in>

Weekly market is not only place for available goods to the villagers but also providing sell opportunity for local agriculture product.

Weekly markets in Karad Taluka:

Karad Taluka have 216 villages and 19 weekly market places. Karad is a taluka of Satara district, Below the table show the detail of weekly market and distance from nearest town/ city of karad.

Issues and Challenges of the weekly markets:

Distance:

In the rural area to be big distance between village and market that why people cannot go to nearest market place so he prefers to weekly market for purchase necessary goods. In study area 17.1 percent weekly village market to nearest statutory town distance is 1-10 km, 26.8 percent village distance is 10-20 km and 56.1 percent village distance is more than 20 km. Table -2 show the details.

Table -2: Weekly Market lists of Karad Taluka of Satara district

Sr. No	District Name	Village Name	District (Distance in km)	Nearest Statutory Town (Name)	Nearest Statutory Town (Distance in km)
1	Satara	Pal	28	Karad	32
2	Satara	Umbraj	37	Karad	17
3	Satara	Masur	43	Karad	15
4	Satara	Charegaon	39	Karad	20
5	Satara	Shirawade	41	Karad	15
6	Satara	Wadgaon Haveli	60	Karad	09
7	Satara	Shenoli	79	Karad	13
8	Satara	Tambve	57	Karad	11
9	Satara	Kole	64	Karad	08
10	Satara	Kolewadi	69	Karad	10
11	Satara	Wing	70	Karad	10
12	Satara	Kale	71	Karad	15

13	Satara	Ond	73	Karad	15
14	Satara	Nandgaon	26	Karad	10
15	Satara	Mhasoli	80	Karad	22
16	Satara	Undale	76	Karad	18
17	Satara	Belawade Bk.	74	Karad	18
18	Satara	Yelgaon	84	Karad	19
19	Satara	Karad	59	Karad	00

SOURCE: <http://www.censusindia.gov.in/2011census>

2. Gender Empowerment:

Table -3: No of sellers in the weekly markets

Sr.No	Weekly Markets	Male	Female	Total
1	Pal	116	47	163
2	Kale	201	115	316
3	Masur	110	34	144
4	Charegaon	72	18	90
5	Nandgaon	39	4	43
6	Shirawade	83	22	105
7	Shenoli	169	52	221
8	Tambve	37	20	57
9	Kole	85	49	134
10	Ond	19	07	26
	Total	931 (71.67%)	368 (28.33%)	1299 (100%)

Source: Field work

In weekly market as a seller female proportion participation is very low. Table – 1 Shows that 71.67% of the seller are male and only 28.33% of the seller are female.

3. Drinking water facilities at Working place:

In the market place pure drinking water facilities like hand pump and other availabilities only 30% markets, table -4 shows the drinking water facilities availabilities in the weekly markets.

Table – 4: Drinking water in weekly Market

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	3	30
No	7	70
Total	10	100

Source: Field work

4. Washroom facilities:

In the weekly markets only 10% availability of toilet facilities market, it is very poor condition and buyers and seller

both face the problem in the market day of unable facilities. Chart -5 shows the toilet facilities in the market area.

Table – 5: Washroom facilities

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	1	10
No	9	90
Total	10	100

Source: Field work

5. Lights facilities:

No electricity connection in the weekly markets, seller arrange own light facilities.

6. Shade facilities:

Only 20% shade facility available in the weekly market, sellers face challenge in the rainy and summer season. Table -5 show the detail

Table-6: Shade facilities in the weekly markets

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	2	20
No	8	80
Total	10	100

Source: Field Work

7. Concrete Road Facilities:

Concrete Road Availabilities In The Weekly Market Are Only 30percent,

Soseller And Buyers Faced Many Problems In Rainy Season To Carry Their Goods Easily. Table -6 Shows The Detail Below

Table -7: Concrete Road Facilities In The Weekly Markets

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	3	30
No	7	70
Total	10	100

Source: Field Work

8. Parking Facilities And Space:

Buyers And Sellers Come With Their Vehicles At The Market Place. In The Weekly Markets Parking And Space Is Good

Role Play And Attract To Him Also. Below The Table Show The Parking Facilities Availabilities In The Market Place

Table -8: Parking Facilities And Space In The Weekly Markets

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	5	50
No	5	50
Total	10	100

Source: Field Work

Conclusion:

Weekly markets important role plays in rural areas providing employment and weekly market sellers in their activity. The study found that they do not have adequate infrastructure facilities at their working place. The government should support to encourage their activity. In Maharashtra more than 70% population lives in rural area and state per capita income is increasing so demand in rural area continue increasing day by day. Weekly market is providing good opportunities for rural area.

income generation. This study examines the issues and challenges faced by the

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